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ANTICANCER, ANTIMICROBIAL AND ANTIOXIDANT BIOACTIVE FACTORS DERIVED FROM MARINE FUNGAL ENDOPHYTES; A REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

The marine-derived fungi has proven to be a very rich source of extremely potent compounds that have demonstrated a number of biologically active compounds with varying degrees of action such as anticancer, antioxidant, anti proliferative and anti microbial properties. These compounds are of interest as new lead structures for medicine as well as for plant and animal self defense. This review is an attempt to consolidate the latest studies in this field, and to showcase the immense competence of marine microbial flora and fauna as bioactive metabolite producers.

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INTRODUCTION

Endophytes are microorganisms that reside asymptotically in the tissues of higher plants and are a promising source of novel organic natural metabolites exhibiting a variety of biological activities. The term “endophytes” includes a suite of microorganisms that grow intra and/or intercellular in the tissues of higher plants without causing any adverse effects to the plants in which they live, and have proven to be rich sources of bioactive natural products (1). The main emphasis of this review is on bioactive compound producing marine fungi and their biological active compounds. Approximately 3,00,000 plant species growing in unexplored area on the earth are host to one or more endophytes(2), and the presence of bio diverse endophytes in huge number plays an important role on ecosystems with greatest biodiversity, for instance, the tropical and temperate rainforests (3), which are extensively found in Brazil and possess almost 20% of its biotechnological source(4). In recent years, marine fungi have been explored more intensely to obtain novel and biologically active compounds, when compared with marine sponges and bacteria. Cephalosporin C was the first bioactive compound from *Cephalosporium acremonium* which was isolated from a sewage outlet of the Sardinian coast(5).

Previous literature shows that marine derived fungi have been recognized as one of the tapped sources for new biologically active secondary metabolites including antitumor, antibacterial, antiviral, antifungal, anti-inflammatory and anticancer activities and enzyme inhibitor compounds. Clodepsipeptide isolated from the marine fungus, *Clonostachys* sp. is having anticancer activity(5). Recent review by Newman and Cragg(6) presented a list of all approved agents from 1981 to 2006, from which a significant number of natural drugs are produced by microbes and/or endophytes. Endophytes provide a broad variety of bioactive secondary metabolites with unique structure, including alkaloids, benzopyranones, chinones, flavonoids, phenolic acids, quinones, steroids, terpenoids tetralones, xanthenes, and others (7). Such bioactive metabolites find wide ranging application as agrochemicals, antibiotics, immunosuppressants, antiparasitics, antioxidants, and anticancer agents (8).

This paper focuses particularly on the role of endophytes in the production of bioactive compounds, the importance of including endophytic microbes in the screening approach for novel drugs, and the microbial biotransformation process as a novel alternative method to obtain such compounds. It also describes these compounds by different functions, including some examples that illustrate the potential for human use. The different methods to obtain bioactive compounds includes extraction from a natural source, microbial production *via* fermentation, or microbial transformation. Extraction from natural sources have few disadvantages such as dependency on seasonal, climatic and political features and possible ecological problems involved with the extraction, thus in need for innovative approaches to obtain novel compounds(9). Hence, biotechnological techniques using different microorganisms appear promising alternatives for establishing cost-effective and renewable resource of high value bioactive products and aroma compounds. The biotransformation method has a huge number of applications (10), for instance, it has been extensively used for the production of volatile compounds(9, 11, 12). These volatile compounds possess not only sensory properties, but other useful properties such as antimicrobial (vanillin, essential oil constituents), antifungal and antiviral (some alkaloids), antioxidant (eugenol, vanillin), somatic fat reducing, blood pressure regulating(2-[E]-hexenal), anti-inflammatory properties (1,8-cineole), and others (13).

Bioactive compounds from marine derived fungi

Marine derived fungal strains produce polyketide derived alkaloids, terpenes, peptides and mixed biosynthesis compounds which are representative groups of secondary metabolites produced by fungi. Miriam et al. (2012) isolated marine-derived fungal strains(14), they yielded several bioactive secondary metabolites among which are *E*-4-methoxy-5-3-methoxybut-1-enyl)-6-methyl-2*H*-pyran-2-one, a new metabolite isolated from the *Penicillium paxilli* strain MaG)K, Norlique xanthone, also known as 1, 3,6-trihydroxy-8-methyl-9*H*-xanthen-9-one, was isolated from the fungus *P. raistrickii* obtained from the sponge *Axinella cf. corrugate*. The structure and absolute stereochemistry of *S*-8-methoxy-3,5-dimethylisochroman-6-ol, isolated from *Penicillium steckii* obtained from an algae belonging to the genus *Sargassum*, could be established by analysis of spectroscopic data and also by comparison with literature data.

A *Penicillium* sp. strain DG M3) 6°C, isolated from the ascidian *Didemnum granulatum*, yielded 13-deoxy-phomenone. Roridin A was isolated from *Trichoderma* sp. obtained from the sponge *Mucaleangulosa* and also identified by analysis of spectroscopic data and comparison with literature data. The fungal strain Ma G) K, obtained from the sponge *M. Angulosa* and identified as *Penicillium paxilli*, gave an extract which was cytotoxic against MDA-MB435 human mammalian cancer cells (HCT8 human colon), CNS 295 central nervous system cancer cells and HL60 leukemia cells. Fractionation of this crude extract yielded three 2-pyrones, belonging to Pyrenocines the class of pyrenocines, of which two were known and one was a new natural product, Pyrenocine J. B and A were first isolated from *Pyrenochaeta terrestris* and identified by spectroscopic and X-ray diffraction analysis (14). Two new indole alkaloids, 2-3, 3-dimethylprop-1-ene) costaclavine and 2-3, 3-dimethylprop-1-ene)-epicosta-clavine, together with the known compounds costaclavine, fungaclavine A and C, were isolated from the marine-derived fungus *Aspergillus fumigates*(15). *Penicillium commune* SD-118, a fungus obtained from a deep sea sediment sample, resulted in the isolation of a known antibacterial compound, xanthocillin X, and 14 other known compounds comprising three steroids, two ceramides, six aromatic compounds and three alkaloids (Table 1).

Table 1. Antibacterial compounds from marine derived fungi (16).

No	Source	Metabolite	Class of compound
1	<i>Emericella unguis</i>	Guisinol	Depside
2	<i>Curvularia lunata</i> <i>Emericella varicolor</i> <i>E. varicolor</i>	Lunatin 1) Cytoskyrin A 2) Varixanthone Shamixanthone, Tajixanthone hydrate, Terrein	Anthraquinone
3	<i>Trichoderma virens</i>	Trichodermamide B	Dipeptide
4	<i>Paraphaeosphaeria</i> sp N-119	Modiolides A-B	Macrolide
5	<i>Cladosporium herbarum</i>	Sumiki's acid, Acetyl Sumiki's acid	Furan carboxylic acid
6	<i>Aspergillus versicolor</i>	Aspergillitine	Chromone derivative
7	<i>Stilbella aciculosa</i>	Fusidic acid	Steroid
8	<i>Ascochyta licorniae</i> <i>Phoma</i> sp	Ascosalipyrrolidinone A Phomadecalins A-D, Phomadecalin A, B, D	Alkaloid
9	Unidentified marine-derived fungus	Seragikinone A	Anthracycline related pentacyclic compound
10	<i>Fusarium</i> sp. <i>Coniothyrium</i> sp isolated from the sponge <i>Ectyplasiaperox</i>)	Neomangicol B 2-hydroxymethyl furan)	Sesterterpenes

Xanthocillin X was isolated for the first time from a marine fungus. In the bioassay, xanthocillin X displayed significant cytotoxicity against MCF-7, HepG2, H460, Hela, Du145 and MDA-MB-231 cell lines. Meleagrins exhibited cytotoxicity against HepG2, Hela, Du145 and MDA-MB-231 cell lines. This is the first report on the cytotoxicity of xanthocillin X (17). Khoulood and Yousry (2012) isolated new biologically active metabolites against some virulent fish pathogens *Edwardsiella tarda*, *Aeromonas hydrophila*, *Vibrio ordalii* and *Vibrio anguillarum*. *Aspergillus terreus* var. *Africanus* was identified as the most potent isolate (18). Acremolin, a novel modified base, was isolated from the culture broth of the marine fungus *Acremonium strictum*. Based on combined spectroscopic analyses, the structure of this compound was that of a methyl guanine base containing an isoprene unit. In addition, the presence of a 1H-azirine moiety is unprecedented among natural products. This compound exhibited weak cytotoxicity against an A549 cell line (19).

In investigation of new bioactive natural products from marine fungi collected from the South China Sea one terrestrial fungal metabolite, chrodriamanin B, together with five new phenolic bisabolane type sesquiterpenoids were isolated from the fermentation broth of a marine-derived fungus *Aspergillus* sp. This is the first report of the isolation of chrodriamanin B from a marine organism (20). S. metanina et al. (2011) determined that the biologically active compounds among marine isolates of microscopic fungus (21). *Myceliophthora lutea* Costantin, which was isolated from marine sediments of Sakhalin Bay Sea of Okhotsk, synthesizes compounds with antibacterial and cytotoxic activities. The new compounds isoacremine D and acremine were reported for the first time from the marine isolate of the fungus *Myceliophthora lutea*. It was found that acremine A in CHCl₃ was converted through the action of light into spiro compounds called as spiro acremine A and B (21). A new cyclopentanopyridine alkaloid, 3-hydroxy-5-methyl-5,6-dihydro-7H cyclopenta(b)pyridin-7-one, together with 11 known aromatic compounds were isolated from the secondary metabolites of the halo tolerant fungal strain *Wallemia sebi* PXP-89 in 10% NaCl (22).

Anticancer compounds

Cancer is a group of diseases characterized by unregulated growth and spread of abnormal cells, which can result in death if not controlled (23). It has been considered one of the major causes of death worldwide: 7.4 million (about 13% of all deaths) in 2015 (23). The anticancer drugs show nonspecific toxicity to proliferating normal cells, possess enormous side effects, and are not effective against many forms of cancer (24, 25). Thus, the cure of cancer has been enhanced mainly due to diagnosis improvements which allow earlier and more precise treatments (25).

There are some evidences that bioactive compounds produced by endophytes could be alternative approaches for discovery of novel drugs, since many natural products from plants, microorganisms, and marine sources were identified as anticancer agents (26). The anticancer properties of several secondary metabolites from endophytes have been investigated recently. Following, some examples of the potential of endophytes on the production of anticancer agents are cited.

The isolation of Taxol producing endophyte *Taxomyces andreanae* has provided an alternative approach to obtain a cheaper and more available product via microorganism fermentation (27). After that, Taxol has also been found in a number of different genera of fungal endophytes either associated or not to use, such as *Taxodium distichum* (28); *Wollemia nobilis* (29); *Phyllosticta spinarum* (30); *Bartaliniaro billardoides* (24); *Pestalotiopsis terminaliae* (31); *Botryodiplodia theobromae* (32).

Another important anticancer compound is the alkaloid “Camptothecin” ($C_{20}H_{16}N_2O_4$), a potent antineoplastic agent which was firstly isolated from the wood of *Camptotheca acuminata* Decaisne (Nyssaceae) in China(33). Camptothecin and 10-hydroxy camptothecin are two important precursors for the synthesis of the clinically useful anticancer drugs, topotecan, and irinotecan(34). Although it's potential use in medical treatments, the unmodified Camptothecin suffers from drawback that compromises its applications due to very low solubility in aqueous media and high toxicity (35, 36). On the other hand, some Camptothecin derivatives retain the medicinal properties and can show other benefits without causing over drawbacks in some cases (37, 38). Therefore, it is desirable to develop strategies for isolation, mixture separation, and production of Camptothecin and its analogues from novel endophytic fungal sources. The anticancer properties of the microbial products Camptothecin and two analogues (9-methoxycamptothecin and 10-hydroxycamptothecin) were already reported. The products were obtained from the endophytic fungi *Fusarium solani* isolated from *Camptotheca acuminata* (38). Several reports have described other Camptothecin (or analogues) producing endophytes (39-43). Since then, endophytes have been included in many studies purposing new approaches for drug discovery.

“Phenylpropanoids” have attracted much interest for medicinal use as anticancer, antioxidant, antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, and immunosuppressive properties (44). Despite the phenylpropanoids belong to the largest group of secondary metabolites produced by plants, reports showed the production of such compounds by endophytes. The endophytic *Penicillium brasilianum*, found in root bark of *Melia zedarach*, promoted the biosynthesis of phenylpropanoid amides (45). Likewise, two monolignol glucosides, coniferin and syringin, are produced not only by the host plant, but were also recognized by the endophytic *Xylariaceae* species as chemical signals during the establishment of fungus-plant interactions (46). Koshino and coworkers characterized two phenylpropanoids and lignin from stromata of *Epichloetypina* on *Phleumpretense*(47).

“Lignans” are other kinds of anticancer agents originated as secondary metabolites through the shikimic acid pathway and display different biological activities that make them interesting in several lines of research (48). Although their molecular backbone consists only of two phenylpropane units (C6-C3), lignans show enormous structural and biological diversity, especially in cancer chemotherapy (44). “Podophyllotoxin” ($C_{22}H_{20}O_8$) and analogs are clinically relevant mainly due to their cytotoxicity and antiviral activities and are valued as the precursor to useful anticancer drugs like etoposide, teniposide, and etopophos phosphate(49). The aryl tetralignans, such as podophyllotoxin, are naturally synthesized by *Podophyllum* spp., however, alternative sources have been searched to avoid endangered plant. Another study showed a novel fungal endophyte, *Trametes hirsute*, that produces podophyllotoxin and other related aryltetra lignans with potent anticancer and properties (50). Novel microbial sources of Podophyllotoxin were reported from the endophytic fungi *Aspergillus fumigatus* Fresenius isolated from *Juniperus communis* L. Horstmann (49), *Phialocephala fortinii* isolated from *Podophyllum peltatum*(51), and *Fusarium oxysporum* from *Juniperus recurva* (37).

“Ergoflavin” ($C_{30}H_{26}O_{14}$), a dimeric xanthene linked in position 2, belongs to the compound class called ergochromes and was described as a novel anticancer agent isolated from an endophytic fungi growing on the leaves of an Indian medicinal plant *Mimus opselengi*(Sapotaceae) (52). “Secalonic acid D” ($C_{32}H_{30}O_{14}$), a mycotoxin also belonging to ergochrome class, is known to have potent anticancer activities. It was isolated from the mangrove endophytic fungus and observed high cytotoxicity on HL60 and K562 cells by inducing leukaemia cell apoptosis (53).

Crude Extracts of *Alternaria alternata*, an endophytic fungus isolated from *Coffea arabica* L., displayed moderate cytotoxic activity towards HeLa cells *in vitro*, when compared to the dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) treated cells (54). The investigation of endophytic actinomycetes associated with pharmaceutical plants in rainforest reported 41 microorganisms from the genus *Streptomyces* displayed significant antitumor activity against HL-60 cells, A549 cells, BEL-7404 cells, and P388D1 cells (55). The screening of endophytic fungi isolated from pharmaceutical plants in China showed that 13.4% endophytes were cytotoxic on HL-60 cells and 6.4% on KB cells (56). Finally, other compounds with anticancer properties isolated from endophytic microbes were reported such as “cytoskyrins” (57), “phomoxanthenes A” and “B” (56), “photinides A-F” (58), “rubrofusarin B” (59), and “(+)-epiepoxydon” (60).

Antimicrobial Compounds

Metabolites bearing antibiotic activity can be defined as low molecular weight organic natural substances made by microorganisms that are active at low concentrations against other microorganisms (61). Endophytes are believed to carry out a resistance mechanism to overcome pathogenic invasion by producing secondary metabolites (7). So far, studies reported a large number of antimicrobial compounds isolated from endophytes, belonging to several structural classes like alkaloids, peptides, steroids, terpenoids, phenols, quinines, and flavonoids (62). The discovery of novel antimicrobial metabolites from endophytes is an important alternative to overcome the increasing levels of drug resistance by plant and human pathogens, the insufficient number of effective antibiotics against diverse bacterial species, and few new antimicrobial agents in development, probably due to relatively unfavourable returns on investment (62, 63). The antimicrobial compounds can be used not only as drugs by human kind but also as food preservatives in the control of food spoilage and food borne diseases, a serious concern in the world food chain (64).

Many bioactive compounds, including antifungal agents, have been isolated from the genus *Xylaria* residing indifferent plant hosts, such as “sordaricin” with antifungal activity against *Candida albicans*(65); “mellisol” and “1,8-dihydroxynaphthol 1-O- α -lucopyranoside” with activity against herpes simplex virus-type 1 (66); “multiploides A and B” with activity against *Candida albicans*(67). The bioactive compound isolated from the culture extracts of the endophytic fungus *Xylaria* sp. YX-28 isolated from *Ginkgobiloba* L. was identified as “7-amino-4-methylcoumarin”(64). The compound presented broad-spectrum inhibitory activity against several food borne and food spoilage microorganisms including *S. aureus*, *E. coli*, *S. typhimurium*, *S. enteritidis*, *A. hydrophila*, *Yersinia* sp., *V. anguillarum*, *Shigella* sp., *V. parahaemolyticus*, *C. albicans*, *P. expansum*, and *A. niger*, especially to *A. hydrophila*, and was suggested to be used as natural preservative in food (64).

Aliphatic compounds, frequently detected in cultures of endophytes, often show biological activities. Four antifungal "aliphatic compounds" were characterized from stromata of *E. typhina* on *P. pratense* (68, 69). Two novel ester metabolites isolated from an endophyte of the eastern larch presented antimicrobial activity. One compound was toxic to spruce budworm (*Choristoneura fumiferana* Clem.) larvae, and the other may serve as potent antibacterial agent against *Vibriosal monicida*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Staphylococcus aureus* (69). Chaetomugilin A and D with antifungal activities, were isolated from an endophytic fungus *C. Globosum* collected from *Ginkgo biloba* (70). Cytosporone B and C were isolated from a mangrove endophytic fungus, *Phomopsis* sp. They inhibited two fungi *C. albicans* and *F. oxysporum* with the MIC value ranging from 32 to 64 mg·mL⁻¹ (71). An endophytic *Streptomyces* sp. from a fern-leaved grevillea (*Grevillea teridifolia*) in Australia was described as a promising producer of novel antibiotics, "kakadumycin A" and "echinomycin". Kakadumycin A is structurally related to echinomycin, a quinoxaline antibiotic, and presents better bioactivity than echinomycin especially against Gram positive bacteria and impressive activity against the malarial parasite *Plasmodium falciparum* (72).

Among the 12 secondary metabolites produced by the endophytic fungi *Aspergillus fumigates* CY018 isolated from the leaf of *Cynodon dactylon*, "asperfumoid", "fumigaclavine C", "fumitremorgin C", "physcion", and "helvolic acid" were shown to inhibit *Candida albicans* (73). Endophyte *Verticillium* sp. isolated from roots of wild *Rehmannia glutinosa* produced two compounds "2,6-Dihydroxy-2-methyl-7-(prop-1E-enyl)-1-benzofuran-3(2H)-one", reported for the first time, and "ergosterol peroxide" with clear inhibition of the growth of three pathogens including *Verticillium* sp. (74). An endophytic fungus *Pestalotiopsis theae* of an unidentified tree on Jianfeng Mountain, China, was capable of producing "Pestalotheol C" with anti-HIV properties (75). Other secondary metabolites with antimicrobial properties isolated from endophytic microbes were reported like "3-O-methylalaternin" and "altersolanol A" (76), "phomoenamides" (77), "phomodione" (78), "ambuic acid" (79), "isopestacin" (2), and "munumbicin A, B, C" and "D" (80).

Antioxidant Compounds

The importance of compounds bearing antioxidant activity lays in the fact that they are highly effective against damage caused by reactive oxygen species (ROS) and oxygen-derived free radicals, which contribute to a variety of pathological effects, for instance, DNA damages, carcinogenesis, and cellular degeneration (81, 82). Antioxidants have been considered promising therapy for prevention and treatment of ROS linked diseases as cancer, cardiovascular disease, atherosclerosis, hypertension, ischemia/reperfusion injury, diabetes mellitus, neuro degenerative diseases (Alzheimer and Parkinson diseases), rheumatoid arthritis, and ageing (83). Many antioxidant compounds possess anti-inflammatory, antiatherosclerotic, antitumor, antimutagenic, anticarcinogenic, antibacterial, or antiviral activities in higher or lower level (84-87).

Natural antioxidants are commonly found in medicinal plants, vegetables, and fruits. However, it has been reported that metabolites from endophytes can be a potential source of novel natural antioxidants. Liu and co-workers evaluated the antioxidant activity of an endophytic *Xylaria* sp. isolated from the medicinal plant *Ginkgo biloba* (88). The results collected indicated that the methanol extract exhibited strong antioxidant capacity due to the presence of "phenolics" and "flavonoids" compounds among 41 identified compounds. Huang and coworkers investigated the antioxidant capacities of endophytic fungal cultures of medicinal Chinese plants and its correlation to their total phenolic contents. They suggested that the phenolic content were the major antioxidant constituents of the endophytes (89).

"Pestacin" (C₁₅H₁₄O₄) and "isopestacin", 1,3-dihydroisobenzofurans, were obtained from the endophytic fungus *Pestalotiopsis microspora* isolated from a plant growing in the Papua New Guinea, *Terminalia morobensis* (90, 91). Besides antioxidant activity, pestacin and isopestacin also presented antimycotic and antifungal activities, respectively. Pestacin is believed to have antioxidant activity 11 times greater than Trolox, a vitamin E derivative, primarily via cleavage of an unusually reactive C-H bond and to a lesser extent, O-H abstraction (91). Isopestacin possess antioxidant activity by scavenging both superoxide and hydroxy free radicals in solution, added to the fact that isopestacin is structurally similar to the flavonoids (90).

"Graphis lactone A", a phenolic metabolite isolated from the endophytic fungus *Cephalosporium* sp. IFB-E001 residing in *Trachelospermum jasminoides*, demonstrated to have free radical scavenging and antioxidant activities *in vitro* stronger than the standards, butylated hydroxytoluene (BHT) and ascorbic acid, co assayed in the study (92). For more detailed information on antimicrobial, antioxidant, and anticancer agents from microbial source, the references Newman and Cragg (6) and Fir'akov'a and coworkers (26) are recommended.

CONCLUSION

Endophytes have proven to be rich sources of novel natural compounds with a wide spectrum of biological activities and a high level of structural diversity. The use of endophytes as biocatalysts in the biotransformation process of natural products assumes greater importance. However, the application of microorganisms by the food and pharmaceutical industries to obtain compounds of interest is still modest, considering the great availability of useful microorganisms and the large scope of reactions that can be accomplished by them.

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